

Selection Criteria: Collaborative Lesson Development Training (CLDT) Call

Building digital skills training and lesson development capacity in the Netherlands NES domain (DC4NES) Project | 2026

About the DC4NES project

The DC4NES (Digital Capacity for Natural and Engineering Sciences) project builds digital skills training capacity in the Netherlands. It is funded by TDCC-NES and runs for two years, starting in December 2025. The project funds 3 teams of 2-3 people to join the Carpentries Collaborative Lesson Development Training (CLDT). There is a single open call, open May – July 2026. The training will take place in November 2026.

The CLDT equips participants with the skills to develop pedagogically sound, reusable, and openly licensed lesson materials in a collaborative manner. Completed lessons are published in the Carpentries Incubator, where they are freely available to instructors worldwide. [The Carpentries website](#) provides further details for this training. The training for one team, consisting of two to three participants, is valued at approximately EUR 5,000–6,000. The training is conducted in English by Carpentries Trainers Johan Hidding and Toby Hodges. The time investment of the training is 16 hours, excluding preparation time.

Selection criteria

The Carpentries Coordinators Network NL will serve as the selection committee in case of oversubscription. Selection will be based on:

- Novelty and added value of the proposed lesson relative to existing [Carpentries Incubator](#) content and existing [Carpentries lessons](#).
- Expected audience size: preference for lessons with a wide potential user base.
- Whether the lesson would be suitable for a beginner audience (an audience with limited experience programming). At least one of the lessons (proposed by one team that will be selected) should be developed for a beginner audience.
- Team diversity: preference for teams with members from different institutions.

Related documents

You can find all related documents in the Digital Capacity for NES community on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/communities/dc4nes>

- Selection Criteria: CLDT Call
- Selection Process: CLDT Call